

Employees Training and Development at MGSSK Ltd Bhalki

BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA

Hod And Associate Professor, Department of MBA, Lingaraj Appa Engineering College Bidar

Abstract- Preparing might be viewed as a subsidizing in the association of human resources. Also, preparing is thought about a helpful gadget for the advancement of creative innovation, commercial center resistance, hierarchical construction, and segment exchange. Preparing and advancement comprises of three essential exercises: instruction, preparing, and improvement. Organizations that offer worker tutoring and advancement make a genuine venture for their representatives. Among the constructive outcomes, this financing will expand the amount of representatives predictable with specialist. In a quickly changing over overall market, described by expanding innovative advances, organizations request a more prominent adaptable and able labor force so as to be versatile and stay forceful. Henceforth, the call for a certified assemblage of laborers will turn into an essential objective. The tutoring and human guide improvement (P&P) machine of a venture is to accomplish authoritative objectives and make forceful increase (Peterafl 18). Representatives put resources into human resources in the wake of beginning business, and commonly this financing is known as training, given the guide of the organization inside the occupation, or got by means of the laborer (and the business) through professional schooling. Subsequently, the standard reason for schooling and advancement is to work on the pleasant of the learner, figuring longings for assorted cravings and techniques for accomplishing them. There are positive rules that ought to be customized by means of offices to ensure that instruction brings about exchange inside the work environment. Preparing decisions and moves should be learned by utilizing generally speaking execution the board frameworks, vital arranging systems, and profession improvement drives.

I. INTRODUCTION

MAHATMA GANDHI SAHAKARI SAKKARE KARKHANE LTD become situated in 2003 underneath the unique chief Dr.Bhimanna khandre. The assembling unit started with an agreeable local area machine. The organization has multiple hundred workers along with authoritative and specialized specialists. Human sources are the most crucial property in an assembling unit, all endeavors to build the impetus and proficiency phases of staff.

The MGSSK LTD entered the sugar industry in April 1991, based in the India, state Karnataka, it began its operation by setting up one sugar industries which used a scientific method for the cultivation of sugarcane, despite increasing emphasis on traditional cultivation method. MGSSK ltd was among few to introduced modernity to this MGSSK Ltd. Is now one of the largest white crystals sugar production in India. The sugar venture in India talented environment that fell due diminished market expense of overall/home to assembling charges are higher, in light of the fact that the stock charge of sugar better are controlled by various specialists the u . S . A . Through SAP (charge advised country) instead of secondary school (value least legal) that reported by means of the Indian specialists it has started sure measures alongside legitimization of sugarcane rate, operationalization of predetermination trade and others. Which targets to complete sugar control is additionally offered through the sugar send out big business. To tide off the overabundance of sugar shares, the Indian government has allowed three trades for sugar trade inside what's to come.

Sugar is the most vital agro undertaking in India and has become a market in the US's financial framework the advancement strategy changes of the Indian specialists are hurriedly in progress and are changing over the monetary scene in the US of america inside

the country. In any case, it appears to be that the breezes of advancement and liberation have now coursed through other mechanical areas which have gone through the sugar endeavor.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Training and development preparing and improvement alludes to scholastic exercises in an association that are made to decorate the arrangement and abilities of work force while providing records and training on the most proficient method to complete sure obligations higher.

Importance of training and development

- gives the most best utilization of Human resources
- upgrade capacity advancement
- blast usefulness
- improving hierarchical lifestyle
- upgrade excellent and assurance
- blast benefits
- upgrading corporate ethical quality and picture

Advantages and disadvantages of training and development

Advantages:

1. Help staff grow new abilities and further develop skill.
2. Development the exhibition and efficiency of people and gatherings.
3. Make better than ever canvases positions.
4. Protect work force propelled and increment their degree of commitment.

Disadvantages:

1. It's far a new sensibly expensive approach.
2. There is usually a danger of which once preparing in addition to advancement, faculty may possibly also forestall functioning.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The particular rule objective of the current gander at is to perceive the pretended through sugar cooperatives in the space of Human asset improvement is for staff and the local area. On this way, sugar factories have a

situation with regards to Human valuable asset improvement in Karkhane just as nearby.

- i) Industrial Training Centre (ITC).
- ii) Training programmes for employees.
- iii) School and College.
- iv) Recreational Facilities.

3.1 Need for the study:

The main need to study about the company is to know the company is satisfying the employees through training and development. And providing the good knowledge about the company, training and development will improve the employees knowledge, attention, attitudes towards the respected job.

sooner than saying that age is liable for developing the schooling enter wants for representatives, it must be perceived that there are different components that make commitments to the age. Instruction is similarly significant for the individual turn of events and progression of representatives, which persuades them to artistic creations in a chose organization beside essentially cash. We likewise expect work force to supplant patterns on market patterns, business strategy changes and extra.

Coming up next are the 2 biggest elements that make commitments to expanding schooling and advancement wishes in an enterprise:

1. Change: The word exchange incorporates practically the entire thing. This is one among the greatest components increasing preparing and development needs. Indeed right now there could be an quick connection between typically the two. Substitute closures in preparing in addition to advancement wishes in addition to preparing and development prompts individual in addition to authoritative exchange, in addition to the cycle earnings to improvement. Futhermore one of a new kind is typically the time that upholds the necessity; substitute typically the way organizations job, contend and communicate.
2. Development: : will be certainly again one awesome justification schooling in addition to advancement to visit end up being more noteworthy basic. Cash isn't generally the best help that might be utilized and that is extremely crucial for the century 21. The individuals who work with the office to find more than just an action; they see

comprehensive self - improvement. As an example, otherworldliness and self - center have long been regular all throughout the planet. Individuals find appropriately work inside the discipline that can't be done, nonetheless there are people that perceive themselves. For instance, in passage, a person may likewise join in a course in 'self - mindfulness', which shows up now not to affect execution at artistic creations however to add to the strict pleasantly - being of the extra basic person.

3.2 Objective of the study:

1. To study on effectiveness of Training and Development.
2. To know the perception of the employees regarding training method.
3. To identify how training assists the employee to acquire skill, knowledge, attitude & also enhance the same.
4. To study whether training help to motivate employees & help in avoiding mistake.
5. To study the change in knowledge implementation of ideas in work and behavior of the employee after training program.
6. To find out the level of satisfaction among all employees regarding training and development program in organization.
7. To study the effectiveness of training on the individual level.
8. To find out the shortcoming in training programs if any.

3.3 Scope of study:

The extent of this investigate was currently not extremely far away until M. G. S. S. Ok. LTD. Hunaji comparably best ensured the tutoring and improvement sports embraced via M. G. S. S. Okay. LTD. For his representatives. This examinations is in the principle about current training methods all through the mission here. Conveys tutoring application and doesn't comprise of all HR exercises directed sooner than and subsequent to tutoring. The examination is principally founded on realities provided by means of different. The investigations become done inside the state of an open - finished survey and talked about with the HR and work force director.

But, there is no study conducted so far on the role of training and development towards achieving operational excellence in the manufacturing industry especially the sugar industry. Since sugar industry is a seasonal industry because sugar manufacturing depends on the production of sugarcane which is a seasonal crop.

Therefore the sugar manufacturing takes place only between September to march / April month of a year. Since, there are many constraints, responsible for the further growth of sugar industry, the researcher has opted to work upon this topic first to highlight the importance of training and development in the operational excellence in the sugar industry. The present research work gives a new outlook and a wide scope in the field of training and development.

It helps the manufacturing industry to understand the importance of training and development programmes and also design training sessions in a way to make them more effective in improving the efficiency of the workforce, especially in sugar industry.

The study helps in identifying the strategies of training for bringing long-term development so that the trainees use their potential to the maximum extent possible in achieving operational excellence in the sugar industry. The study also helps in identifying major shortcomings in conducting training and development programmes and finding suitable measures to overcome them. In this way, the study helps the sugar industry to grow more satisfied customers and become market leader. The study also set new guidelines and a better direction to the future researchers, academicians etc. who would be interested to pursue their researches in the similar areas in same or different type of organisations.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Analysis Techniques:

This is the technique selected by me to collect the data from the respondent. For the study scheduled was selected as the instrument for the research work. I have interviewed all the samples personally with the help of developed scheduled to collect the primary data for the research work.

- Primary data: information is aggregated first after which unique. Key information has been obtained from personnel who could have gone through this training method and ability to complete accordingly. Major ideas might be accrued through awareness or through primary verbal business with respondents within a structure or the other or through near home meetings; alluded to as essential records. Essential facts assortment takes a good deal of the time. In this gander at the principle records have been gotten through, interviews with employees director of Mirielle. G. S. Capital t. K. LTD. Hunji.

Primary data can be defined as the first hand information related to any research work. Primary data has been collected by the researcher through original observations, discussions, interviews and field survey etc., by visiting the M.G.S.S.K.LTD. Hunaji many times. These data work together with excellent examinations and awareness that deliver helpful and valuable results. The results, which depend on key information, are pretty much observational associated with extremely gainful cost. Typically the overview became brought with the guide of the experts by way of a review with a condition that secured questions that allows you to choose the adequacy of training and advancement programs towards accomplishing useful achievement in Mirielle. H. S. T. E. LTD. Hunaji

Techniques of primary data collection: -

1. Observation
2. Questionnaire
3. Interviews

- Secondary Data:

These varieties of realities, that can be accrued for different measurements while utilized, is recognized as additional records. Additional data became constructed from the association's office world-wide-web website and from guide books. End up being it optional data submitted or unpublished. Allocated records involves specialised and replace schedules. Books, mags, paperwork and web. Regarding this, earlier view is essential and for this Let me go through different manager information to determine about the items and employees anxious over the part to have the option to straight adapt to the merchandise quickly and not directly. Regarding research, recommended

information sources contain Magazines, Induction guides and data models accessible on the relationship. Optional proportions series calls for even less time since it is as of today to be enjoyed. Optional data variety procedures:

Q.1 Please mention your age:

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
20-25	15	30%
25-30	15	30%
Above 30	20	40%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 30% of workers are referenced 20-25 age to be a piece of this organization,30% of representatives are referenced 25-30 age to be a piece of this association and 40% of representatives are referenced over 30.

Interpretation:

The above table shows larger part of representatives are above 30 and they fell that the accomplishment of the association is a direct result of work arranged representatives.

Q.2 gender

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Male	35	70%
Female	15	30%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 70% male and 30% of female working in an organization.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the larger part is Male. here the male workers are more than female workers

3 to 5 year	20	40%
More than 5 years	15	30%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 30% employees have less than 3-year experience, 40% employees have 3-5years experience, and 30% employees says that they have more than 5 years' experience.

Interpretation:

In this above table maximum employees have 3-5years experience.

Q.3 Marital Status

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Single	20	40%
Married	25	50%
Divorce	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 40% single 50% married 10% divorced employees are there in an organization

Interpretation:

The above table shows that the maximum number of married employees are there.

Q.5 Is this your first organisation?

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	25	50%
No	25	50%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 50% employees responded yes and 50% of employees responded No.

Q.4 No. of years of experience

Particular	Respondent	Percentages
Less than 3 years	15	30%

Interpretation:

In this above table we noted that employees says that 50% yes and 50% No

Q.6 What do you think the training programs will be run in future?

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	35	70%
No	15	30%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 70% of employees responded yes and 30% of employees responded No

Interpretation:

From the above table maximum employees says that yes. Here 70% employees said training program will run in future.

Q.7 Do the Executive Director engage development activities for him/herself?

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	40	80%
No	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 80% of employees responded yes. And 20% of employees responded No.

Interpretation:

Above table shows that maximum employees say that yes. Here they told that executive director engage development activities by himself.

Q.8 Do you feel trust in your supervisors?

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	45	90%
No	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 90% of workers are referenced yes to be a piece of this organization,10% of representatives are referenced No to be a piece of this association

Interpretation:

The above table shows majority of employees is yes. They trust their supervisor

Q.9 Do the practices supervisors use positive attitude with employees?

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	45	90%
No	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 90% of employees responded yes and 10% of employees responded No.

Interpretation:

The above table shows majority of employees is Yes. Here the practices supervisors use positive attitude with employees 90%.

Q.10 Do you feel, you are being paid fairly?

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	40	80%
No	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 80 % of employees Response is Yes and the 20% of employees responded No.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority of employees responded is yes. They think that they are being paid fairly.

Q.11 Does your practice equipment (everything from computer to scale) work properly?

Particular	Respondent	Percentage
Yes	45	90%
No	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 90% of employees responded yes and the 10 % of employees responded No.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority of employees responded is yes. Here they are saying that their practice equipment’s work properly.

Q.12 Does your company use a specific training process?

	Response	Percentage
Yes	45	90%
No	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 90% of employees responded yes and the 10% of employees responded No.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority of employees responded is yes. Here they are saying that the company use specific training process.

Q.13 Do you require a high degree of technology knowledge for your job?

	Response	Percentage
Yes	40	80%
No	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Analysis

From the above table it is tracked down that 80% of employees responded yes and the 20% of employees responded No.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that greater part of representatives reacted is yes. Here they require a serious level of innovation information for their work.

Q.14 Are office conditions comfortable?

	Response	Percentage
Yes	35	70%
No	15	30%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 70% of employees responded yes and the 30% employees responded No.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that majority of employees responded is yes. Here 70% employees are comfortable with their office condition.

Q.15 Do you satisfy with organizational training and development programme?

	Response	Percentage
Yes	45	90%
No	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Analysis:

From the above table it is tracked down that 90% of employees responded yes and 10% of employees responded No.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that greater part of representatives reacted is yes. Here they are happy with the preparation and advancement program.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDING

despite the fact that a major amount of faculty are content material with the way they do, there's still degree to dissect at the miniature stage whether helpless respondents are excluded, faced, pestered, etc. On the chance of those insights there is an extension for remedial development to be taken

1. Collaboration among associates and the degree of help imparted to other each makes a bond with the business undertaking.
2. Training is provided to new join who include fresh graduate.
3. Such training program includes technical & non-technical training programs. Training need is identified through performance appraisal and assessment feedback.
4. Neighborhood direct and language affect is better at some stage in instruction and even subsequent to giving language the favored impact isn't seen.
5. A couple of managers don't bother to make an improvement movement plan and send it to the instruct.
6. The discoveries of the records investigation were that the poll survey affirmed great improvement impacts, advancement and by and large score with respect to the modified schooling.
7. Truth and reproduction training is unquestionably adored with the guide of the faculty who've acquired it.
8. An organization has on full fledge training system, which looks after all the training activities.
9. Training policies of the company has always been good, with the full support of management of workers.
10. 10 Enough practice given to the employee during the training session. 80% employees agree with the practice session.
11. Attitude about training program of employee are positive.
12. Minimum 15-40 days for implementation for trained, knowledge & skills. 40% training is fulfilled.
13. Time is important barrier to training& development in organization.
14. Comments recognized with changes in design and degree for overhauling the following instruction

programming should be examined and tried with the appropriate point.

CONCLUSION

Sugar cooperatives do honorable works of art in Human helpful asset improvement each inside the manufacturing plant and for the organization too. Inside of the training and improvement application for the work push, it became found that handiest specialised staff at 'A' degree were directed by using sending them to schooling institutions like Mahatma Gandhi Sahakar Sakkare Karkhane, Hunaji, Bhalkeshwar Sahakar Sakkare Karkhane, Hallikhed. For different personnel inside the building unit, no outstanding tutoring application is ready. He was outfitted most uncomplicated for measure training. While period is changed or a pristine contraption is snared, the essential manufacturer is approached to give gizmo activity tutoring. For the organization, sugar cooperatives have a dynamite operate HRD via utilizing mechanical training offices, customary universities and resources.

REFERENCES

- [1] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , PERFORMANCE AFFECTING FACTORS OF INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS, George Washington International Law Review, Vol.- 07 Issue -01, April-June 2021, PAGE No : 607-621, Available at: <http://archive-gwilr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Bhadrappa-Haralayya.pdf>
- [2] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY AFFECTING FACTORS IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS, Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI), Vol.- 12 Issue -03, June 2021, PAGE No : 603-620, Available at: <https://www.tojqi.net/index.php/journal/article/view/791/242>
- [3] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , IMPLICATIONS OF BANKING SECTOR ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA, George Washington International Law Review,

- Vol.- 07 Issue -01, April-June 2021, PAGE No : 631-642 Available at: <http://archive-gwilr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Bhadrappa-Haralayya-1.pdf>
- [4] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL ,STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF BANKS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com) ,Volume: 2, Issue: 5, May 2021, Page No : 184-194. Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2105025.pdf>
- [5] Bhadrappa Haralayya ; P. S. Aithal . "Study on Model and Camel Analysis of Banking" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals ,Volume 4 ,Issue 11 ,May 2021 Page 244-259. Available at <https://irejournals.com/paper-details/1702750>
- [6] Bhadrappa Haralayya and Aithal, P. S.. "Analysis of cost efficiency on scheduled commercial banks in India". International Journal of Current Research, Volume 13, Issue 06, June 2021, pp 17718-17725 Available at: <https://www.journalcra.com/sites/default/files/issue-pdf/41580.pdf>
- [7] Bhadrappa Haralayya and P. S. Aithal, "A Study On Structure and Growth of Banking Industry in India", International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management ,Volume 4, Issue 5, May 2021. Page no 225–230. Available at: <https://www.journals.resaim.com/ijresm/article/view/778/749>.
- [8] Bhadrappa Haralayya, Retail Banking Trends in India ,International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM), Volume: 9, Issue: 5, Year: May 2021, Page No : 3730-3732. Available At http://www.ijaresm.com/uploaded_files/document_file/Bhadrappa_Haralayyaqscw.pdf
- [9] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, FACTORS DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR : A TOBIT REGRESSION ANALYSIS", International Journal of Science & Engineering Development Research (www.ijedr.org), Vol.6, Issue 6, June-2021, page no.1 - 6, Available :<http://www.ijedr.org/papers/IJEDR2106001.pdf>
- [10] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , IMPLICATIONS OF BANKING SECTOR ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA, flusserstudies, Volume 30, June 2021,Page No:1068-1080, Available at: <https://flusserstudies.org/archives/801>
- [11] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS, International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology, Volume 8, Issue 1, June-2021 ,Page no: 159 – 164, Available: http://ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT151514_PAPER.pdf
- [12] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , STUDY OF BANKING SERVICES PROVIDED BY BANKS IN INDIA, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com), Volume: 2, Issue: 6, Year: June 2021,Page No : 06-12, Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2106002.pdf>.
- [13] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANK PERFORMANCE USING CAMEL APPROACH", International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (www.jetir.org | UGC and issn Approved), Vol.8, Issue 5, May-2021, page no 305-314, Available at : <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2105840.pdf>
- [14] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, ANALYSIS OF BANK PRODUCTIVITY USING PANEL CAUSALITY TEST, Journal of Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Volume 50, Issue 6, June-2021 , Page no: 1 – 16, Available at: <https://app.box.com/s/o71lh776opeypauvzucp9e5ntjw9zf>
- [15] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, INTER BANK ANALYSIS OF COST EFFICIENCY USING MEAN, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJIRSET), Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021 ,Page no: 6391-6397, Available at: http://www.ijirset.com/upload/2021/june/97_IN

- TER_NC1.pdf
- [16] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY AND PROFITABILITY MATRIX OF BANKS BY HMTFP AND FPTFP, Science, Technology and Development Journal, Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021, Page no: 190-203, Available at: <http://journalstd.com/gallery/23-june2021.pdf>
- [17] BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY BY AGGREGATE LEVEL, Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology, Volume 13, Issue 6, June- 2021 ,Page no: 296-314, available at: <https://www.xajzkjdx.cn/gallery/28-june2021.pdf>
- [18] Bhadrappa Haralayya, P S Aithal, "ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY BY DISAGGREGATE LEVEL", International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), Volume.9, Issue 6, June 2021, pp.b488-b502, Available at :<http://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2106187.pdf>
- [19] Haralayya B. Importance of CRM in Banking and Financial Sectors Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021, 6(1): 8-9
- [20] Haralayya B. How Digital Banking has Brought Innovative Products and Services to India. Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021; 6(1): 16-18
- [21] Haralayya B. Top 5 Priorities That will Shape The Future of Retail Banking Industry in India. Journal of Advanced Research in HR and Organizational Management 2021; 8(1&2): 17-18.
- [22] Haralayya B. Millennials and Mobile-Savvy Consumers are Driving a Huge Shift in The Retail Banking Industry. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 17-19
- [23] Haralayya B. Core Banking Technology and Its Top 6 Implementation Challenges. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 25-27
- [24] Nitesh S Vibhute ; Dr. Chandrakant B. Jewargi ; Dr. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Non-Performing Assets of Public Sector Banks" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals Volume 4, Issue, 12 June 2021, Page 52-61 Available at <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702767.pdf>
- [25] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa and Saini, Shrawan Kumar, An Overview on Productive Efficiency of Banks & Financial Institution (2018). International Journal of Research, Volume 05 Issue 12, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837503>
- [26] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Review on the Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country (2018). Journal for Studies in Management and Planning, Volume 04 Issue 05, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837496>
- [27] Basha, Jeelan and Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Performance Analysis of Financial Ratios - Indian Public Non-Life Insurance Sector (April 30, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837465>.
- [28] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, The Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country With Special Reference to Banks & Financial Institution (april 30, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844432> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844432>
- [29] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Study on Performance of Foreign Banks in India (APRIL 2, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844403> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844403>
- [30] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-Finance and the Financial Services Industry (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844405> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844405>
- [31] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-payment - An Overview (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844409> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844409> .
- [32] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Customer Satisfaction at M/s Sindol Bajaj Bidar" Iconic Research And

- Engineering Journals, Volume 4 ,Issue 12, June 2021, Page 157-169 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702792.pdf>
- [33] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Ratio Analysis at NSSK, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12,June 2021, Page 170-182 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702793.pdf>
- [34] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Financial Statement Analysis of Shri Ram City Union Finance" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12,June 2021, Page 183-196 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702794.pdf>
- [35] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Employee Job Satisfaction at Big Bazaar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 197-206 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702795.pdf>
- [36] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Effect of Branding on Consumer Buying Behaviour at Vijay Bharat Motors Pvt Ltd, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 207-222 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702796.pdf>
- [37] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Customer Perceptions Guru Basava Motors, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12,June 2021, Page 223-231 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702797.pdf>
- [38] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Loans and Advances for DCC Bank Main Branch Nayakaman, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 232-242 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702798.pdf>
- [39] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Work Life Balance of Employees at Karanja Industries Pvt Ltd, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 243-254 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702799.pdf>
- [40] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Working Capital Management at TVS Motors, Bidar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 4, Issue 12, June 2021, Page 255-265 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702800.pdf>
- [41] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Testing Weak Form Efficiency of Indian Stock Market – An Empirical Study on NSE (April 30, 2021). Emerging Global Strategies for Indian Industry (ISBN: 978-81-910118-7-6), 2021, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837488>
- [42] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Top 10 Ways to Improve the Communication Skills (JUNE 20, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844410> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844410>
- [43] Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Multi-Inter-Trans Disciplinary Research Towards Management and Commerce (July 25, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3847404>
- [44] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Advertising Effectiveness With Reference to Big Bazaar" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 5, Issue 1, July 2021, Page 101-110 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702831.pdf>
- [45] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Analysis of Non Performing Asset on Urban Cooperative Bank in India" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 5, Issue 1,July 2021, Page 111-121 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702832.pdf>
- [46] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Ration Analysis With Reference to DCC Bank" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals, Volume 5, Issue 1, July 2021, Page 122-130 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702833.pdf>
- [47] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Consumer Buying Behavior With Reference to Bajaj Auto Ltd" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals,

- Volume 5, Issue 1, July 2021, Page 131-140 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702834.pdf>
- [48] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Sales Promotion With Reference to Yamaha Motor" *Iconic Research And Engineering Journals*, Volume 5, Issue 1, July 2021, Page 141-149 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702835.pdf>
- [49] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Financial Statement Analysis Using Common Size on Mahindra Sindol Motors" *Iconic Research And Engineering Journals*, Volume 5, Issue 1, July 2021 , Page 150-159 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702836.pdf>
- [50] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Loans And Advances with Reference to PKGB Bank" *Iconic Research And Engineering Journals*, Volume 5, Issue 1, July 2021, Page 160-170 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702837.pdf>
- [51] Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Trend Analysis at John Deere" *Iconic Research And Engineering Journals*, Volume 5, Issue 1, July 2021, Page 171-181 Available at: <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702838.pdf>
- [52] Haralayya B, Aithal PS. Study on Cost Efficiency in Indian and Other Countries Experience. *Journal of Advanced Research in HR and Organizational Management* 2021; 8(1&2): 23-30.
- [53] Haralayya B, Aithal PS. Study on Theoretical Foundations of Bank Efficiency. . *Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management* 2021; 4(2): 12-23.
- [54] Haralayya B, Aithal PS. Study on Profitability Efficiency in Indian and Other Countries Experience. *Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management* 2021; 6(2): 1-10.
- [55] S. Vinoth, Hari Leela Vemula, Bhadrappa Haralayya, Pradeep Mamgain, Mohammed Faez Hasan, Mohd Naved, Application of cloud computing in banking and e-commerce and related security threats, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2021,ISSN 2214-7853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.11.121>.(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214785321071285>).
- [56] Haralayya B, Jeelan BV, Vibhute NS. Capital Structure and Factors Affecting Capital Structure. *J Adv Res Eco Busi Mgmt* 2021; 4(2): 4-35.
- [57] Vibhute NS, Haralayya B, Jeelan BV. Performance Evaluation of Selected Banks using Ratio Analysis. *J Adv Res Eco Busi Mgmt* 2021; 4(2): 36-44
- [58] Jeelan BV, Haralayya B, Vibhute NS. A Study on Empirical Analysis of Relationship between FPI and NIFTY Returns. *J Adv Res Acct Fin Mgmt* 2021; 3(2): 3-22
- [59] Jeelan BV, Haralayya B, Vibhute NS. A Study on Performance Evaluation of Initial Public Offering (IPO). *J Adv Res Pub Poli Admn* 2021; 3(2): 12-26.
- [60] Basha VJ, Haralayya B, Vibhute NS. Analysis of Segment Reporting with Reference to Selected Software Companies. *J Adv Res Entrep Innov SMES Mgmt* 2021; 4(2): 9-26.
- [61] Jeelan BV, Haralayya B, Vibhute NS. Co-Movement and Integration among Stock Markets: A Study of 10 Countries. *J Adv Res Acct Fin Mgmt* 2021; 3(2): 23-38.
- [62] Jeelan BV, Haralayya B, Vibhute NS. A Comparative Study on Selected Foreign Currencies. *J Adv Res Eco Busi Mgmt* 2021; 4(2): 45-5